

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**INFANT SLEEP PROBLEMS AND MANAGERMENTS: A REVIEW
OF THE LITERATURE**

Khalid Turki Al-Swalem¹, Mohammed Ali Mousa Zalah², Nedaa Mohammednour Alsamadani^{3,5}, Seham Matar Al-Otaibi⁴, Anmar Mohammed Batawi⁴, Faisal Masoud Al-Matrafi⁴, Azzah Atitallah Al-Zahrani⁵, Abdulaziz Yahya Wafi⁶, Eman Mohammed Al-Otaibi⁶, Hussin AlEid⁷

¹ Surgical Resident, King Saud Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, ² Surgical Resident, Prince Mohammed bin Nasser Hospital, Jazan, Saudi Arabia, ³ Pediatric Resident, Maternal and Children Hospital, Makkah, Saudi Arabia, ⁴ Faculty of Medicine, Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia, ⁵ Faculty of Medicine, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, ⁶ Faculty of Medicine, Taif University, Taif, Saudi Arabia, ⁷ Faculty of Medicine, King Faisal University, Al-Hasa, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Infant sleep problems have been the focus of a growing literature over the last few years. The current review is based on literature searches of Pubmed and PsycInfo for studies published over the last few years including randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews and meta-analyses on infant sleep problems and resulting developmental effected, risk factors and managements. Several risk/protective factors for sleep problems have been identified including health literacy, TV in the room, feeding, close contact and arousing activities at bedtime, intolerance for infant crying, co-sleeping, maternal depression and infant temperament. Cross-cultural differences have been noted both for infant sleep problems and parents' perceived distress by those problems. A number of interventions have been tried to ameliorate infant sleep problems including consultations, teaching sessions on extinction and bedtime fading, internet-based interventions and nighttime massages by parents. Some of these studies have shown improvements and others have suggested only short-term or negligible effects. Significant methodological problems exist with this literature including the almost sole use of parent report as well as the mixed age samples and the potential confounding variables.

Keywords: *Infant, Sleep, Problems, Managements, Review.*

Corresponding author:**Khalid Turki Al-Swalem,***Surgical Resident, King Saud Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.*

QR code

Please cite this article in press Khalid Turki Al-Swalem et al., *Infant Sleep Problems And Managements: A Review Of The Literature.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(02).

INTRODUCTION:

Infant sleep problems have been the focus of a growing literature over the last few years. This narrative review is based on literature searches of Pubmed and PsycInfo for studies published over the last few years including randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews and meta-analyses on infant sleep problems and their resulting developmental effects, risk factors and interventions.

Infant sleep problems have been noted to affect a significant per cent of infants and have been major management problems for both parents and pediatricians [1]. Stability within individuals has been reported for sleep patterns, suggesting that the problems may continue and affect later development. Several risk/protective factors for sleep problems have been identified including health literacy, TV in the room, close contact, feeding and arousing activities at bedtime, intolerance for infant crying, co-sleeping, maternal depression and infant temperament [2-10]. Cross-cultural differences have been noted both for infant sleep problems and parents' perceived distress by those problems. A number of interventions have been tried to ameliorate infant sleep problems including consultations, teaching sessions on extinction and bedtime fading, internet-based interventions and bedtime massages by parents [11-22]. Some of these studies have shown improvements and others have suggested only short-term or negligible effects. Significant methodological problems exist with this literature including the almost sole use of parent report as well as the mixed age samples and the potential confounding variables [23-27].

METHODOLOGY:

Sample

We performed comprehensive search using biomedical databases; Medline, PsycInfo and

Pubmed, for studies concerned with placenta previa published between 2013- 2019 in in English language. Keywords used in our search through the databases were as {Infants, Sleep, Management, and risk factors}. More relevant articles were recruited from references lists scanning of each included study.

Analysis

No software was used, the data were extracted based on specific form that contain (Title of the study, name of the author, Objective, Summary, Results, and Outcomes). Double revision of each author outcomes was applied to ensure the validity and minimize the errors.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION:

Risk and protective factors for infant sleep problems

Several risk and protective factors for infant sleep problems have been researched over the last few years including health literacy, television in the same room, bedtime feedings, close contact at bedtime, arousing activities at bedtime, emotional availability, bedtime routine, parent regulation, intervention delays, co-sleeping (bed-sharing), maternal depression and infant temperament (see Table 1 for a list of risk and protective factors for infant sleep problems). Although most of these risk factors involve parental management of bedtime activities/routines, more general parental lifestyle problems include health literacy and sleeping environment. Most of the recent studies have noted multiple risk factors, and cross-cultural differences have been reported for virtually all of the risk factors. Further, maternal depression and infant temperament have been noted to mediate these risk factors for infant sleep problems [1-27].

Table 1. Risk/protective factors for infant sleep problem

Risk/protective factors	Sleep outcome	Authors
TV in bedroom	<nighttime sleep	Bathory et al
>maternal emotional availability <close contact, <nursing, <arousing bedtime activities	> sleep	Philbrook & Teti (2016a)
>maternal emotional availability <co-sleeping	< cortisol levels	Philbrook & Teti (2016b)
>father caregiving	>sleep mothers & infants	Tikotsky et al
>intolerance infant crying	> sleep problems	Sadeh et al
>finger sucking	<nightwakings	Butler et al
> co-sleeping	>nightwakings	Volkovich et al
>co-sleeping Asian countries	<sleep	Mindell et al. (2010)
>feeding at bedtime & evening TV	>nightwakings	Ahn et al
>bedtime routines	<nightwakings > sleep	Mindell and Lee (2015)
>prenatal depression	<deep sleep > indeterminate sleep	Field et al
>depression and anxiety	<sleep	Petzoldt et al
>hypersensitivity and >hyposensitivity	<sleep quality	DeMarcus et al

Interventions for infant sleep problems

Most of the recent intervention studies for infant sleep problems have involved educational/behavioral interventions including consultation on sleep physiology and strategies to improve infant sleep, group teaching along with support calls, graduated extinction and bedtime fading (see Table 2 for a list

of interventions for infant sleep problems). Included here are randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews and a meta-analysis that are briefly reviewed along with an internet-based intervention for infant and toddler sleep disturbances and studies on massage therapy by mothers [28-33].

Table 2. Interventions for infant sleep problems

Interventions	Results	Authors
Self-settling skills	<nightwakings	Symon & Crichton
No physical contact during crying	<maternal depression and stress	
Bedtime routines, minimal stimulation, controlled comforting, no co-sleeping	<sleep problems	Hall et al
Graduated extinction	<cortisol, <sleep onset	Gradisar et al
Bedtime routine (bath/massage/cuddling)	<nightwakings, <sleep onset	Mindell et al. (2009)
Internet-based and internet-based plus bedtime routine (bath/massage/cuddling)	<nightwakings, <sleep onset,> sleep	Mindell et al. (2011)
Behavioral techniques review	>sleep	Chrichton & Symon
Massage by mothers	>night sleep, >melatonin	Ferber et al
Lotion massage by Mothers	>sleep Ms & Is	Field et al. (2016)

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses on sleep managements

Very few studies have addressed the effects of behavioral interventions during the first six months which is surprising. If there is notable stability of sleep patterns across the first six months [34], it would seem that those interventions would be most effective the earlier they were applied. In a literature search on the use of behavioral techniques for infant sleep during the first six months, 11 studies were identified of which eight demonstrated improvements in infant sleep outcomes [29]. Although the 8 of 11 studies showing improvement speaks to the efficacy of early intervention, it is surprising that only 11 studies could be found on behavioral interventions

for sleep during the first six months. Parents may expect their infants to have sleep problems over the first six months and possibly do not seek consultation as frequently as parents of older infants. Also, the behavioral techniques that have been developed may require the greater sophistication of older infants and toddlers. Infant researchers focusing on the first six months have successfully modified other behaviors of very young infants, suggesting the possibility and the need for further development of behavioral intervention strategies for sleep behaviors of younger infants. Several randomized controlled trials have demonstrated positive effects of behavioral interventions on infant sleep measures. However, authors of systematic reviews and meta-analyses have

questioned the effectiveness of behavioral sleep interventions. In a systematic review, for example, by British authors using the PubMed and Cochrane Databases to identify systematic reviews, meta-analyses, clinical trials and cohort studies on behavioral sleep interventions for infants younger than six months, the authors concluded that behavioral interventions had decreased infant crying, prevented sleep or behavioral problems or postpartum depression [35].

DISCLOSURE:

No conflicts of interests with respect to the authorship or publication of this article.

REFERENCES:

- Ahn, Y., Williamson, A. A., Seo, H. J., Sadeh, A., & Mindell, J. A. (2016). Sleep patterns among South Korean infants and toddlers: Global comparison. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*: 31., 261–269.
- Bathory, E., Tomopoulos, S., Rothman, R., Sanders, L., Perrin, E. M., Mendelsohn, A., et al. (2016). Infant sleep and parent health literacy. *Academic Pediatrics*: 16., 550–557.
- De Marcas, G. S., Soffer-Dudek, N., Dollberg, S., Bar-Haim, Y., & Sadeh, A. (2015). Reactivity and sleep in infants: A longitudinal objective assessment. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*: 80., 49–69.
- Field, T., Diego, M., Hernandez-Reif, M., Figueiredo, B., Schanberg, S., & Kuhn, C. (2007). Sleep disturbances in depressed pregnant women and their newborns. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 30., 2007.
- Field, T., Field, T., Cullen, C., Largie, S., Diego, M., Schanberg, S., et al. (2008). Lavender bath oil reduces stress and crying and enhances sleep in very young infants. *Early Human Development*: 84., 399–401.
- Field, T., Diego, M., & Hernandez-Reif, M. (2010). Moderate pressure is essential for massage therapy effects. *International Journal of Neuroscience*: 120., 381–385.
- Field, T., Gonzalez, G., Diego, M., & Mindell, J. (2016). Mothers massaging their newborns with lotion versus no lotion enhances mothers' and newborns' sleep. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 45., 31–37.
- Field, T., Diego, M., Dieter, J., Hernandez-Reif, M., Schanberg, S., Kuhn, C., et al. (2004). Prenatal depression effects on the fetus and newborn. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 27., 216–220.
- Field, T., Hernandez-Reif, M., Diego, M., Feijo, L., Vera, Y., & Gil, K. (2004). Massage therapy by parents improves early growth and development. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 27., 435–442.
- Mindell, J. A., & Lee, C. (2015). Sleep, mood, and development in infants. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 41., 102–107.
- Mindell, J. A., Telofski, L. S., Wiegand, B., & Kurtz, E. S. (2009). A nightly bedtime routine: Impact on sleep in young children and maternal mood. *Sleep*: 32., 599–606.
- Mindell, J. A., Sadeh, A., Wiegand, B., How, T. H., & Goh, D. Y. T. (2010). Cross-cultural differences in infant and toddler sleep. *Sleep Medicine*: 11., 274–280.
- Mindell, J. A., DuMond, C. E., Sadeh, A., Telofski, L. S., Kulkarni, N., & Gunn, E. (2011). Efficacy of an internet-based intervention for infant and toddler sleep disturbances. *Sleep*: 34., 451–458.
- Mindell, J. A., Leichman, E. S., Composto, J., Lee, C., Bhullar, B., & Walters, R. M. (2016). Development of infant and toddler sleep patterns: Real-world data from a mobile application. *Journal Sleep Reserach*,. Epub ahead of print.
- Mindell, J. A., Leichman, E. S., DuMond, C., & Sadeh, A. (2016). Sleep and social-emotional development in infants and toddlers. *Journal of Clinical Child and Adolescent Psychology*: 5., 1–11. Epub ahead of print.
- Mindell, J. A., Li, A. M., Sadeh, A., Kwon, R., & Goh, D. Y. (2015). Bedtime routines for young children: A dose-dependent association with sleep outcomes. *Sleep*: 38., 717–722.
- Mindell, J. A., Sadeh, A., Kwon, R., & Goh, D. Y. (2015). Relationship between child and maternal sleep: A developmental and cross-cultural comparison. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*: 40., 689–696.
- Petzoldt, J., Wittchen, H., Einsle, E., & Martini, J. (2016). Maternal anxiety versus depressive disorders: Specific relations to infants' crying, feeding and sleeping problems. *Child Care Health and Development*: 42., 231–245.
- Philbrook, L. E., & Teti, D. M. (2016a). Bidirectional associations between bedtime parenting and infant sleep: Parenting quality, parenting practices, and their interactions. *Journal of Family Psychology*: 30., 431–441.
- Philbrook, L. E., & Teti, D. M. (2016b). Associations between bedtime and nighttime parenting and infant cortisol in the first year. *Developmental Psychobiology*,. Epub ahead of print.
- Sadeh, A., Mindell, J., Luedtke, K., & Wiegand, B. (2009). Sleep and sleep ecology in the first 3 years: A web-based study. *Journal of Sleep*

- Research: 18., 60–73.
22. Sadeh, A., Tikotzky, L., & Scher, A. (2010). Parenting and infant sleep. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*: 14., 89–96.
 23. Sadeh, A., De Marcas, G., Guri, Y., Berger, A., Tikotzky, L., & Bar-Haim, Y. (2015). Infant sleep predicts attention regulation and behavior problems at 3–4 years of age. *Developmental Neuropsychology*: 40., 122–137.
 24. Sadeh, A., Juda-Hanael, M., Livne-Karp, E., Kahn, M., Tikotzky, L., Anders, T. F., et al. (2016). Low parental tolerance for infant crying: An underlying factor in infant sleep problems? *Journal of Sleep Research*, Epub ahead of print.
 25. Sadeh, A. (2004). A brief screening questionnaire for infant sleep problems. Validation and findings for an internet sample. *Pediatrics*: 113., 570–577.
 26. Tikotzky, L., Sadeh, A., Volkovich, E., Manber, R., Meiri, G., & Shahar, G. (2015). Infant sleep development from a 3–6 months postpartum: Links with maternal sleep and paternal involvement. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*: 80., 107–124.
 27. Volkovich, E., Ben-Zion, H., Karny, D., Meiri, G., & Tikotzky, L. (2015). Sleep patterns of co-sleeping and solitary sleeping infants and mothers: A longitudinal study. *Sleep Medicine*: 16., 1305–1312.
 28. Symon, B., & Crichton, G. E. (2016). The joy of parenting: Infant sleep intervention to improve maternal emotional well-being and infant sleep. *Singapore Medical Journal*, Epub ahead of print.
 29. Crichton, G. E., & Symon, B. (2016). Behavioral management of sleep problems in infants under 6 months—What works? *Journal of Developmental and Behavioral Pediatrics*: 37., 164–171.
 30. Hall, W. A., Hutton, E., Brant, R. F., Collet, J. P., Gregg, K., Saunders, R., et al. (2015). A randomized controlled trial of an intervention for infants' behavioral sleep problems. *BMC Pediatrics*, Epub ahead of print.
 31. Hall, W. A., Liva, S., Moynihan, M., & Saunders, R. (2015). A comparison of actigraphy and sleep diaries for infants sleep behavior. *Front Psychiatry*, Epub ahead of print.
 32. Gradisar, M., Jackson, K., Spurrier, N. J., Gibson, J., Whitham, J., Williams, A. S., et al. (2016). Behavioral interventions for infant sleep problems: A randomized controlled trial. *Pediatrics* (Epub Ahead of Print).
 33. Ferber, S. G., Laudon, M., Kuint, J., Weller, A., & Zisapel, N. (2002). Massage therapy by mothers enhances the adjustment of circadian rhythms to the nocturnal period in full-term infants. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioral Pediatrics*: 23., 410–415.
 34. Figueiredo, B., Dias, C. C., Pinto, T. M., & Field, T. (2016). Infant sleep-wake behaviors at two weeks, three and six months. *Infant Behavior and Development*: 44., 169–178.
 35. Douglas, P. S., & Hill, P. S. (2013). Behavioral sleep interventions in the first six months of life do not improve outcomes for mothers or infants: A systematic review. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioral Pediatrics*: 34., 497–507.